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Ivona Mladineo

BCAS

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Executive Summary

Cure4Aqua is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme and aims to support the EU aquaculture industry through the activities that involve several trials, tests and development of tailored tools/ protocols focusing on a variety of fish species, such as European seabass (ESB), gilthead seabream (GSB), common carp (CC), rainbow trout (RBT) and Senegalese sole (SS). The project will develop solutions for prioritized pathogens of the marine (NNV, *Vibrio* spp., *Tenacibaculum maritimum*, *Aeromonas veronii*, *Piscirickettsia salmonis*, *Midichloria*, other *Chlamydiae*, *Sparicotyle chrysophrii*) and freshwater fish aquaculture (CEV, KHV, IPNV, *Flavobacterium psychrophilum*, *Tetracapsuloides bryosalmonae*, *Sphaerospora molnari*), building also on progress already achieved in previous EU funded projects, as well as on biotechnological and bioengineering innovations for humans (aptamers, phage therapy, tissues bioprinting, drug delivery through nanocarriers). Therefore, Cure4Aqua will follow rights and responsibilities related to data management as stated in article 17 Grant Agreement, so that the research data generated in the action is managed responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles. For this reason, the project will adhere to the maxim "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" when dealing with data. The data management plan (DMP) is a living document, which will be updated during the project. This is the second version written in M18 as deliverable D1.3 and will be updated two more times, at M36 (D1.4), and M54 (as D1.5). The application of this document is the responsibility of all Cure4Aqua project partners.

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1. Data Summary

Cure4Aqua data management plan (DMP) follows the rights and responsibilities related to data management as set in article 17 Grant Agreement so that the research data generated in the action is managed responsibly and in line with the FAIR principles. The application of this document is the responsibility of all Cure4Aqua project partners. Adhering to the maxim "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" when dealing with data, Cure4Aqua will develop DMP as a living document, which will be updated during the project. The current is the second version written in M18 as deliverable D1.3 and will be updated two more times, at M36 (D1.4), and M54 (as D1.5). In brief, expected data to be generated within Cure4Aqua range from metagenomic, transcriptomic and proteomic data of immune response analyses, welfare and health data, disease economic impacts, vaccine formulation data, pathogen culture data, antigen (recombinant protein and transcript level) validation data, pathogen or recombinant protein concentrations, pathogen/ adjuvant ratios, pathogen inactivation regime data, biosecurity score data, data relating to challenge models used, fish condition factors and survival data, antibody level data, Fluidigm array and flow cytometry, statistical analysis, pathology, gene expression (qRT-PCR), histology and IHC data, amongst others. Third-party data include questionnaire replays, scoring and ranking data, opinions and reports, and production data, while literature prospecting data include collections of publications, extracted metadata and consequent analytics outputs.

1.1 Types of data

For easy orientation, the data to be generated have been grouped according to specific WP.

1.1.1 WP2

- Validated health-related performance and success indicators (SI) used in human and animal health management and key success indicators (KSI) for aquaculture subsectors (CC, ESB, GSB, RT);
 - Health-related KPIs are based on those already developed and validated for fish (GSB, ESB) in the project PerformFish (<https://zenodo.org/records/4551512>).
 - The Key Success Indicators (KSI) have been collected and evaluated by the internal experts in WP3 and will be used by the Moderator Group during the Delphi sessions with the Process Group (PG). Their validation by the PG Vaccines was performed in early April.
<https://3.basecamp.com/5521393/buckets/30629545/vaults/7323392415>
- Bibliographic search on the relevance of published information on aquatic animal diseases and discrimination according to authorship, year of publication and area covered (matching with the topics of the different WPs of Cure4Aqua);
 - Scientists were identified:
 - via citations in the Scopus database,
 - via editorial boards of renowned scientific journals published in Europe and indexed by the Journal Citation Reports (JCR) in the section Fisheries,

quartiles Q1 through Q2. From these journals, all European editorial board members were collected.

- A list of experts was identified via governmental publications and reports identified in the AGRICOLA database and the CAB abstracts database (aquaculture reports).
- Business owners and consultant companies were identified via the following sources with the help of AI:
 - Social Media: Posts, comments, and discussions from various social media platforms like X, Facebook, etc.
 - Wikipedia: Articles and content from the multilingual encyclopaedia Wikipedia, which covers a vast range of topics.
 - News Articles: News articles from diverse news sources and outlets, providing information on current events and historical context.
 - Websites: Content from websites across the internet, including blogs, company websites, and other online sources.
 - Forums: Discussions and conversations from online forums and message boards like Reddit and Quora.

A detailed procedure has been stored in Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/10889646>

- Bibliographic search on global warming effects and extracted metadata (pH, salinity, oxygen, temperatures, diseases observed in field/ *in vitro*/ *in vivo*, clinical signs, pathology, morbidity/ mortality); Traditional research methods were employed for Task 2.2, including searches via Google and Scopus, along with the assessment of reference lists from relevant articles and reviews, resulting in the inclusion of over 400 references in the current form of the review. Respective data is stored at <https://zenodo.org/records/10889690>. Bibliographic search on alternative and conventional bacterial and parasitic management and extracted metadata (risks, such as pharmacokinetics, retention in the environment, consumer safety; cost-benefits, such as frequency of use, price; and efficiency);
- List of diseases (OIE, relevant emerging), disease ranking criteria, and disease ranking; bibliographic research on the Burden of Diseases in aquaculture and extracted metadata;
- Questionnaires and interviews with PG, operational economic model, willingness to pay questionnaires on vaccines, alternative treatments and other Cure4Aqua solutions;
- Data on intracellular bacteria models: sampling, dual transcriptomics, etiology, pathogenesis; data on *in vitro* infection of bioprints.

1.1.2 WP3

- Data on *A. veronii* and *T. maritimum* collections, *in silico* characterisation of vaccine targets;

Twenty *A. veronii* and 30 *T. maritimum* and *Tenacibaculum* spp. isolates have been selected for sequencing. These are representative stains from larger collections held in -80 °C freezers

(alarmed and monitored) at HCMR and MRI respectively. It is foreseen that the sequences will be generated by FGCZ by 6/2024 and consequently uploaded into Zenodo.

- Data on recombinant capsid protein of natural reassortant strains RGNNV/SJNN, and tandem repeated NNV-coat protein epitopes from RGNNV and SJNNV strain;

The VNNV protein-based vaccine has been designed using the complete SpSslAusc160.03 betanodavirus capsid protein sequence. GenBank accession no. FJ803923 (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/FJ803923>).

- Sequencing data of CEV isolates from diseased carp, proteomic and transcriptomic data from diseased carp;

The first antigen selection dataset has been added to Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/10828049>.

- *T. bryosalmonae* immunogenic epitopes, transcriptomics of infected host cells and epitopes, *T. bryosalmonae* vaccine candidates;

Seven orphan antigens have been shortlisted and will be uploaded to Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/11032203>.

- Vaccine data (monovalent and bivalent NNV recombinant proteins vaccine, NNV mRNA vaccine, *A. veronii* inactivated whole-cell vaccines, *A. veronii* recombinant universal protein vaccine, CEV dodecine-based vaccine, CEV mRNA vaccine, two *T. maritimum* inactivated vaccines, *T. bryosalmonae* recombinant proteins vaccine);
- Data on vaccine delivery methods (microcarriers and nanoparticles encapsulation, immersion delivery, intraperitoneal and intramuscular injection, immersion combined with low-frequency sonophoresis);
- Vaccine efficiency trial in laboratory and field (challenge tests) and related data (serum antibody levels, qPCR of immune genes expression).

1.1.3 WP4

- Data on fish groups for epigenetic and phages/ probiotic testing (genotyping, growth, FCI), data on the undertaken challenge (poly I:C, handling stress);
- Transcriptomic, miRNA expression, methylation data of challenged fish, metagenome sequencing data;
- Bibliographic search on epigenetic and microbiome markers in aquaculture, selected epigenetic markers, and protocol for selective breeding programs based on epigenetic markers.

1.1.4 WP5

- Zootechnical data of the larval rearing process (growth and survival of the fish);
- Genomic sequencing and functional data of *Vibrio* spp. and *F. psychrophilum* phages; optimised bioreactor protocol;

- Data on anti-*F. psychrophilum* probiotic bacteria; data on pathogen-antagonistic effects of various phage/ probiotic combinations;

Phage production trials with bioreactors is uploaded in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/10972688>.

- Data of fish challenge (delivery efficiency, effects on pathogen control, microbiota composition, long-term effects on fish gut microbiota, fish health and survival);
- Genomic and phenotypic data of phage/probiotic resistant bacteria;
- MIC and MBC of anisaxin in G-negative aquaculture bacteria isolates, nanocarrier properties and encapsulation efficiency, anisaxin pharmacokinetics, data from fish challenge testing (survival/ mortality), transcriptomic data of challenged fish;

Uploaded in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/10852753>.

- Data on passive immunisation with VRLB recombinant antibody against NNV (fish data, viral load, NNV neutralisation in cell lines).

1.1.5 WP6

- Data (from cages) of fish spatiotemporal swimming performance, welfare indicators and morphometric characteristics, improved algorithms and new algorithms (for skin, eye, tail and operculum status), RT data from environmental sensors, predictive models;

Data containing analysis for the correlation between behavioral and environmental data for the ESB, for the summer period of 2022 and 2023 is stored at: <https://zenodo.org/records/10842740>;

- Data on broodstock status, including steroid and cortisol concentrations in seawater, gonadal biopsies, sperm, blood and mucus data, spawning performance, egg and larval quality estimate;

A dataset of water quality parameters (alkalinity, ammonia, nitrates, nitrites, dissolved oxygen, pH, salinity, water temperature) in two flow-through (G1, G2) and two RAS (G3, G4) tanks has been uploaded to Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/10939769>.

Concerning broodstock status, including cortisol and steroid concentrations in both seawater and blood, along with assessments of gonadal biopsies, sperm quality, spawning performance, and egg and larval quality, two sampling exercises have been conducted to this point. Additionally, spawning data are being collected daily, with egg and larval quality data gathered weekly. These extensive datasets are organized and preserved in Excel format.

Once the data compilation is complete and all files are finalized, the comprehensive dataset will be uploaded to Zenodo.

- Protocol for aptamer development for detection of CEV, *Flavobacterium* and MLO, IgT, SCOC3 and cathelicidin proteins, the protocol for the development of ELISA, western blot and flow cytometric assays for respective aptamers;

- Protocol for qPCR on-chip diagnostic tool for *T. bryosalmonae*, *T. maritimum*, KHV, CEV, NNV, IPNV, data on collected samples (water, skin, sera) and sensitivity testing;

Selection of the markers for Integrated microfluidics (IMF) platforms is stored at: <https://zenodo.org/records/10828092>

- Protocol for the development of Integrated fluidic circuit (IFC), the protocol for the development of nanoscale RT-qPCR/qPCR, metagenomic data of fish;
- Protocol for three fish bioprints development, SOP for three fish bioprints, PoC testing of bioprints with pathogens.

1.1.6 WP7

- Bibliographic search on multidisciplinary operational welfare indicators for aquaculture fish and in certain cases of terrestrial livestock, identified and validated welfare indicators, mini-Delphi data on welfare indicators, data on three WSs;

The systematic literature review is provided at: <https://3.basecamp.com/5521393/buckets/30724532/vaults/7010419677>

Video and graphical materials from the 1st Delphi Workshop in Athens (24.-25.11.2023): <https://3.basecamp.com/5521393/buckets/30724532/vaults/7319293000>

- Data on Quality of Life scaling system, including veterinary and behaviour-monitoring interventions, humane endpoints to reduce suffering, and indicators for the assessment of the state of consciousness and death;
- Data on new operational welfare score index, validated welfare indicators, data on field trials of new OWI, data on developed welfare assessment tool;
- Data on the stress status of farmers and their perception of fish welfare with metadata (questionnaires); model for estimation of impact among fish welfare, environmental impact and farmer's well-being; data for the welfare certification scheme;
- Data on biosecurity audits and assessment protocols, farmers' data including questionnaires, data for developing the scoring system, and biosecurity certificates;
- Data from a group of experts from online questionnaires;
- Data from a panel of experts replying to multiple iterative questionnaires to reduce the range of responses and gain consensus based on criteria chosen a priori by researchers of the WP7 team.

1.1.7 WP8

- Data from DEC including generated material, data on events, social media outreach, and publications;

DEC materials have been uploaded in Basecamp (Protocols for Pre-dissemination, Prior Notice procedure, IP Assessment Form):

<https://3.basecamp.com/5521393/buckets/30698771/vaults/6468672481>

- Data on training materials, stakeholders' data, and training certificates.

1.1.8 Re-use of the existing data

To generate a part of the highlighted data, partners will need to re-use the existing data. This in particular relates to -omics data stored in public repositories, such as databases hosted by the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI) and the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB). These will be reused for data mining and comparative analysis of data generated by the FGCZ partner, which administrates all project's -omics needs and therefore covers all scientific WPs (WP2-WP6) that will capitalise on genotyping (epigenetics), qPCR, RNA and DNA sequencing, including microbiome sequencing, Whole Genome Sequencing, and proteomics.

In particular, **WP2** will rely on collections from public databases. Data related to diseases' economic impacts and other data necessary for WP2 activities (third-party data of PG members, scientific publications for metadata analyses) will be prospected from scientific literature databases, such as Clarivate, using Journal Citation reports (JCR) and Scopus, PubMed, Agricola database (for publications officially released by governments), and the CAB abstracts database (to extract aquaculture reports by the publishing organisation). This strategy capitalises on the approach published by Ioannidis et al. (2016) and Ioannidis et al. (2020). Unpublished data generated by third parties (for example from other projects) will be used only after an agreement, for mutual benefit/publication. This could be the case for the datasets collected from Mediterranean fish farms through the VRI system managed by ISPRA, and based on open KPI developed in PerformFish (http://performfish.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/D7_1_Approved.pdf).

In **WPS**, data from previous larval rearing trials will be re-used for comparative reasons.

In **WP6**, data has been re-used from relevant publications to provide the background information, comparative analyses or to improve methodologies, e.g., Georgopoulou et al. (2024)¹, Nunez-Bajo et al. (2020)², Dausse et al. (2011)³, Liu et al. (2022)⁴. Omics data from public databases hosted by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) is used for comparative analyses during marker design.

In **WP7**, partners will capitalise on the existing database of stakeholders/ experts, as well as an existing platform for the distribution and analysis of questionnaires (Prorata). Unpublished data (UoC) generated in other self-funded projects on the development of a digital tool to assess the welfare of ESB and GSB will be also used. For biosecurity assessments, existing questionnaires that have been developed for salmon farms will be adapted to suite T7.4 activities. Available pictures of the histopathology (copyright Hamish Rodger, previously VAI, now PathoGen) will be reused as the

¹Georgopoulou D, Vouidakis C and Papandroulakis N 2024. Swimming behavior as a potential metric to detect satiation levels of European seabass in marine cages. *Front Mar Sci*. 11:1350385. doi:10.3389/fmars.2024.1350385

²Nunez-Bajo E, Silva Pinto Collins A, Kasimatis M, Cotur Y, Asfour T, Tanriverdi U, Grell M, Kaisti M, Senesi G, Stevenson K, Güder F 2020. Disposable silicon-based all-in-one micro-qPCR for rapid on-site detection of pathogens. *Nat Commun*. 11:6176. doi:10.1038/s41467-020-19911-6

³Dausse E, Taouji S, Evadé L et al. 2011. HAPIScreen, a method for high-throughput aptamer identification. *J Nanobiotechnol*. 9:25. doi:10.1186/1477-3155-9-25

⁴Liu YS, Deng Y, Chen CK, Khoo BL, Chua SL 2022. Rapid detection of microorganisms in a fish infection microfluidics platform. *J Hazard Material*. 431:128572

training material.

Data reuse of existing own data sets of partners is considered background information and will be included in the Consortium Agreement. Likewise, partners involved in WP2 (T2.4), WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 will use their yet unpublished in-house data to enable comparative omics studies. *E.g.*, SWU will use their unpublished data on Nile tilapia epigenetics response to stress for comparisons with rainbow trout and seabass.

1.2 Data format and size

Table 1: Data types and format

TYPE	EXTENSION
containers	tar, gzip, zip
databases	xml, csv, xls
geospatial	shp, dbf, geotiff, netcdf
statistics	ascii, dta, por, sas, sav, graphpad, spss, r, stat, mat
images	tiff, jpeg, pdf, png, eps, bmp, ppt, mov, mpeg-4, avi
tabular	csv, tsv, fcs, eds, xml, sds, OpenArray
text	xml, txt, pdf, html, ascii, utf-8, json, docx
omics	fasta, fastaq, bam, vcf, nwk

Types and formats of data that Cure4Aqua will generate and re-use a range from numeric (*e.g.*, databases, spreadsheets, questionnaires, index score); textual (*e.g.*, text-editing files, sequences (FASTA), lab books, handbooks, documents, open access scientific publications), images (*e.g.*, video, pictures, animation), big metadata files (including QC data) from NGS, proteomics, AI outputs, genomic sequences, amongst others.

In **WP2**, data will be in numeric (*e.g.*, databases, spreadsheets, questionnaires, index score) and textual, in .docx and .xls format.

In **WP3**, as well as other WPs (**WP2 T2.4**, **WP4-WP6**) that will use -omics approaches, raw sequencing data and transcriptomic studies will be available in standard format (.fastq, bam, vcf), while processed tables will be made available in tab/ comma delimited format (.tsv, .csv), such as the phylogenetic trees in Newark (.nwk) format. Data from statistical analyses will be collected in a variety of file formats, mainly R (.R) and Microsoft Excel (.xls). Databases will be stored in Open Document Format or as CSV files to enable sharing and long-term validity of the data. Immunological and microbiological data will be in the form of raw and relative numerical data (qPCR), absolute numerical data (*e.g.*, raw optical density readings) and will be stored in Microsoft Excel spreadsheets as well as in hard copy.

WP5 will generate numerical data in .xls format related to the zootechnical aspects of the fish trials. The same format will be used also for phage microbiology (phenotypic characterization) and the Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations/ Minimum Bactericidal Concentrations of anisaxin in fish bacterial pathogens, the pharmacokinetics of anisaxin in treated fish and fish challenged by a bacterial pathogen (mortality/ survival tables). Data related to the generation of the nanocarrier for anisaxin

encapsulation will be reused from the partner's data (CU), available in numeric (.xls) format. Fasta and Fastq formats will be used for the genomic data.

WP6 will generate numerical data related to environmental parameters (temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH), fish husbandry (quantity of feeding, time and date of cage cleaning and treatments), and images and video from fish in cages to derive fish biometrics (measurements of fish length, width), health status measures (fin and opercula integrity, eye condition) and behavioural traits (swimming speed, feed consumption), as well as spawning performance data (sperm and egg quality). Simulation data will be generated from the analyses (numerical or text format). Selex processes for the design of aptamers will apply fastq data, while qPCR on chip/ in lab will produce quantitative data. Selex data will generate data on nucleic acid molecules (nt sequences) binding to specific pathogens, qPCR on chip and microfluidic data include data on pathogen quantification and functional immune activities of blood and mucus.

Given that for the Delphi Workshops and the research included in **WP7** for the perceptions of certain target groups, both quantitative and qualitative methods will be used, the types of data for qualitative are binary, nominal, and ordinal; while for quantitative methods, data are basic statistics, descriptive and inferential. More details will be updated in this section when the exact format of the Delphi Workshops is defined and when the drafts of the questionnaires are ready.

WP8 will generate numerical scores in biosecurity audits and identify hazards (and level of risk). These may be entered into a confidential database for benchmarking purposes within the industry, which will be compiled in excel.

The purpose of **data re-use** is to serve as the background to facilitate research activities in all WPs' tasks, such as selection of SI on aquatic animal health and their evolution (**WP2**); antigen detection and variation in different strains, vaccine formulation, vaccine efficacy testing (**WP3**); identification of epigenetic and microbial data related to fish health/ welfare (**WP4**); application of anisaxin in fish feed, comparison with previous trials, comparison with other phages/ bacteria isolates (**WP5**); improved automated monitoring of the health and welfare status of the farmed fish. Data will also be applied to optimize rapid molecular detection assays for fish pathogens and immune markers, including multiplexing fluidic platforms (**WP6**). Partners in WP6 will use existing data algorithms and previously registered patented applications to build on and further develop these systems (*e.g.*, partner HCMR uses patent 1010400/03.02.2023 developed within PerformFish to improve and modify camera output analyses and AI algorithms). In **WP7** (T7.4) for example, similar types of farming sites (flow-through pond farms, RAS units (freshwater), RAS (marine), pen sites (marine), flow-through freshwater and marine tank sites) can be compared or benchmarked against others in a region, country and between geographic regions, therefore the industry can see where they reside compared to peers. This can generate improvements in site biosecurity as well as identify specific hazards which can be addressed.

In terms of **size**, it is foreseen that data files will range from a few MB's to up to 50 TB. The estimation for -omics data (**overall WPs**) is that the raw sequencing data will result in up to 25 million reads, 15 Gb data MiSeq or 5 billion reads, 1.5 Tb data HiSeq, and transcriptomic data up to 40 M reads and 12 Gb data.

WP2 Search is composed of several searches and is derived from the combination of these files. As a general rule, the final products are around 20 Mb large. For the first 12-month period the estimated size was about 2 TB for the ESB videos and for the period between January 2023 and January 2024. The respective data for the GSB was 900 GB for the period between June 2023 and February 2024 (**T6.1**). Molecular data and textual data presently amount to about 250 GB.

Table 2: Data re-used from projects

PROJECT	DATA RE-USE
AquaMed (2010-2013) FP7 ID: 244999	Identified aquaculture sustainability indicators and KPI to be used in (T2.1).
Fishboost (2014-2019) FP7 ID: 613611	Identified important microbial diseases for European aquaculture and genetic approaches for their mitigation (T2.1, T2.3).
ParaFishControl (2015-2020) H2020 ID: 634429	Transcriptomic and genomic data of non-model parasites for assisting antigen discovery (T3.1). Green therapeutics, infection models, transfer between caged and farmed fish parasites using ddRAD-Seq (T2.2, T2.3).
AQUAPHAGE (2010-2015) Marie Curie (IRSES)	Established research network on phage therapy in aquaculture, including collaborative experimental work and researchers exchange program (T4.1 and T5.1).
EPIMARK (2018-2020) H2020 ID: 812986	Commercial feasibility of a kit for the identification of epigenetic markers in farmed fish: Validated growth epimarkers in Nile tilapia (T4.1, T 4.2).
ProAqua (2014-2019) Danish Innovation Foundation	Explored probiotic bacteria and phages against <i>Vibrio anguillarum</i> in turbot and cod larvae, and their live feed (T5.1).
PerformFish (2017-2022) H2020 ID: 727610	Tools for fish growth assessment (T6.1). Identified KPI and KSI, best therapeutic practices, OWI, code of conduct and good practices in aquaculture (T2.1, T2.2, T3.2, T7.1, T7.5).
FishiENCI (2014-2020) H2020	Developed the first algorithms for fish growth and swimming performance (T6.1).
MedAid (2017-2021) H2020 ID: 727315	Established operational welfare indicator (OWI) profile for GSB and ESB (T7.1-T7.4).
Aquaplan (2008-2011) Marine Research Sub- Programme	Developed biosecurity plans and best farm practice, including codeveloper and co-author Farmed Salmonid Health Handbook (T7.5 and T8.4).
EPIFISH (2016-2022) ERC Consolidator Grant	Identified novel epigenetic markers for fish domestication, optimised RRBS method for teleost genomes, identified miRNAs, DNA methylation/ hydroxymethylation and microbiome changes linked to fish domestication (T4.1 and T4.2).
BactiVac Network (2018) GCRF	Nano-immersion vaccine against columnaris disease: developed a nanotechnology platform to increase the solubility, stability, biocompatibility, and permeability of a formalin-killed <i>F. columnare</i> immersion vaccine, with a muco-adhesive chitosan biopolymer (T3.2 and T5.3).

COPEWELL (2011-2015) FP7	Evaluated the basic mechanisms involved in coping strategies of fish towards improvement of welfare (T7.1-T7.4).
SALHEARTCELL (2020-2023) Federal Ministry of Education and Research Germany	Developed and used functional 3D salmonid heart cultures for detection and replication of difficult to culture salmonid viruses (Piscine orthoreovirus 1 and 3, Salmonid alphavirus 2 and 3, Piscine myocarditis virus) (T6.3).

The **origin and provenance of data** are from Process Groups questionnaires, primary and secondary scientific publications and governmental reports, farm reports and collected data (**WP2**), vaccination trials *in vivo* (**WP3**), fish tissues sequencing (**WP4**), survival/ mortality testing, other phages and bacteria publicly available (**WP5**), sensors/ cameras located in the experimental facility of HCMR, lab and sampling protocols and their adaptations (**WP6**), stakeholders' questionnaires, biosecurity audits and assessments (**WP7, WP8**).

Data utility outside Cure4Aqua will be collected and recorded in an organized manner at regular intervals from the foreseen stakeholders. The latter un-exhaustively include relevant academic community and researchers within the industry, farmers with breeding programs (Finnforel, AquaGen, Troutlodge, Salmobreed, Avramar, Sysaaf, Cromaris), diagnostic companies (MSD Animal Health, RPC, FishFarm Solutions), animal welfare organisations and benchmarking associations, consumers, policymakers or other decisions makers (*e.g.*, FEAP, National Producers' Associations, Animal Welfare Associations, Consumer Associations, Government Bodies), animal feed producers (such as Biomar, Skretting, Veronesi, Lallemand), nanomaterial companies (InnoCore, NanoCarrier, Nanoshel), bioengineering companies (Fluicell, Cellinks, Aspect Byosystems), research laboratories carrying out diagnostic services and the entities/ individuals who provide veterinary advice and services.

2. FAIR data

Cure4Aqua generated and collected data will be open access and 'FAIR', that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable, unless there are justified reasons for opting out, which will then be given in the DMP *e.g.*, for IPR or privacy/ data protection concerns.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Cure4Aqua generated and collected data, that do not need IP protection, will be deposited in open online data repositories, making the data findable. For the data storage, we have chosen **Zenodo** (<https://zenodo.org/communities/cure4aqua/>), where the "Community of Cure4Aqua" was set up. When other data will be generated, these will be stored in specific repositories that facilitate the finding, accessing, re-using and inter-operating of data sets, for example, NCBI, EBI ENA, TiHo eLib, Zenodo PRIDE PRoteomics IDentifications (PRIDE) database, ArrayExpress within the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI). Final transcriptomic/ genomic data will be submitted to the Database of Genomic Variants (DGVa). For Cure4Aqua Zenodo repository, data and metadata will be catalogued with the following elements: title, author(s), publication date, description, access right, licence, and funding.

For everyday management of the project, Cure4Aqua uses **Basecamp** (<https://3.basecamp.com/5521393/projects>). To easily navigate datasets, each dataset is assigned a

particular name, which in Basecamp serves as PI and has the following sequence consisting of three different parts separated with a "." (dot) character:

ProjectName.DatasetName.Version, where

- a. The ProjectName is Cure4Aqua, to clearly identify all datasets the origin;
- b. The DatasetName represents the full name of the dataset;
- c. The Version of the dataset represents in which phase of the project the dataset was released.

Basecamp provides a centralized platform for team members to communicate, share files, assign tasks, and track the progress of the project. For each WP, a small project was set up there, primarily with the purpose of efficient communication among the partners and sharing files generated by partners.

The structure of data that will be put into Basecamp can vary depending on each WP. In each WP there is the structure for files (Deliverables/ Minutes of meetings/ Milestones/Datasets). The structure of files will be updated according to the individual needs of each WP in each period. **WP1** which includes Project coordination and management is structured widely since in M18 there is more information and data which are common for all WP (General Assembly, Instructions, Minutes of Meetings, Contact list, Templates, Logos, Grant agreement, Consortium agreement, Milestones, Deliverables). Here are the types of data that are or will be added to Basecamp:

1. Documents: minutes of meetings, agreements, templates, deliverables, milestones, instructions, drafts of documents, and any other important documents related to the project;
2. Images and videos: any visual content related to the project, such as logos, images, and promotional videos;
3. Datasets: spreadsheets, databases and other data generated by the project.

As a **persistent identifier** (PI), data will have a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) maintained by the International DOI Foundation (IDF), which can be generated by all the above-listed repositories. (Meta)data will have a globally unique (assigned to one single specific digital object) and eternally (if the DO is deleted, the PI should remain and point to so-called tombstone information, including basic metadata about the DO's properties) persistent identifier. For omics data, PI will consist of an internet link (*e.g.*, a URL that resolves to a web page that defines the concept such as a particular fish cytokine) and specific PI generated by the database where the sequence or protein has been stored (UniProt, Unique ID, PRJN). For example, all samples submitted by respective WPs to FGCZ partner will be managed using the **B-Fabric platform** (Türker et al. 2011), which is a web-based management system for analytical projects, samples and data, that is developed and operated by the FGCZ. It manages also the unambiguous naming and placing of data files with unique identifiers. Data and result files produced at FGCZ for the Cure4Aqua project will be submitted also to Zenodo, and stored in compliance with the principles of Open Science. For long-term data preservation and sharing, -omics data will also be submitted to public repositories, where unique accession numbers will be assigned. For literature reviews and metadata collection (**WP2**), the Scopus database will be used. In **WP2**, concerning **T2.3** which requires metadata search, no new metadata will be created, but existing

metadata will be collected and curated. Metadata based on molecular biology will be developed in task **2.4** (after M16).

Rich metadata will be provided to allow discovery, including descriptive information about metadata context, quality and condition, or characteristics of the data concerning each WP.

Cure4Aqua will generate **‘intrinsic’ metadata**, such as the data captured automatically by machines that generate data such as DICOM information for image files, as well as raw data (fish behaviour) analysed using machine learning algorithms, big data tools and modelling (**WP6**). The majority will be ‘contextual’ metadata (practically for all WPs), such as optimised and generated new protocols (DNA/ RNA extraction methods, epigenetics library, sequencing protocols, aptamer SELEX process information), obtained measurements (fish, food, survival/ mortality data, antibody titre, OD, CT) and the units of the measured data, species involved (explicitly by taxon id, *e.g.*, <http://www.uniprot.org/taxonomy/9606>), the genes/ proteins/ antibodies (*e.g.*, GO Terms, annotation of functional domains), questions and concepts linked to longitudinal data (**WP7**, **WP8**), calculation of the properties of materials, or any other details about the experiment.

Foreseen **metadata standards** will be those that set the minimum information standards in the form of guidelines and formats for reporting data derived by specific high-throughput methods typical for -omics data. This will ensure the data generated by these methods can be easily verified, analysed and interpreted by the wider scientific community. In addition, this will facilitate their transfer from journal articles (“unstructured data”) into databases (“structured data”) in a form that enables data to be mined across multiple data sets. Cure4Aqua minimal information standards will un-exhaustively include RNAseq (MINSEQE), MIQE (qPCR experiments), proteomics (MIAPE), MIACA (cell-based assays), MIAPAR (protein affinity reagents), MIABE (bioactive entities), MIGS/ MIMS (genome/ metagenome sequencing), MIFlowCyt (flow cytometry), MISFISHIE (*in situ* hybridisation and IHC experiments), MIAPA (phylogenetic analyses), Minimum information reporting in bio–nano experimental literature (Faria et al., 2018), Nanotechnology Standards. For literature scoping, PRISM guidelines will be the standard. **WP6** will follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices and use common standard formats for metadata (*e.g.*, real-time PCR data markup language, RDML for data comparison of quantitative data produced by different qPCR machines).

In addition to these, metadata generated by FGCZ will use B-Fabric to keep track of all samples and meta-information regarding sample treatment and processing in the wet lab. -Omics data submitted to chosen public repositories will be accompanied by the relevant **metadata documentation**, such as the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) Metadata Model (<https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/general-guide/metadata.html>), Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) metadata (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/info/examples/seq_template.xlsx), and NCBI genome metadata (<https://submit.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/about/genome/#step5>). Sequencing data analysed using the FGCZ SUSHI framework will be fully documented, reproducible and reusable, since the results are always accompanied by the executed analysis scripts, the version numbers of the software used, as well as the input and parameters. For custom analysis, analysis results will be also stored together with analysis scripts, which will be version-controlled using the FGCZs git server (<https://gitlab.bfabric.org>). The proteomics datasets as deposited in the chosen data repositories will be accompanied by the relevant metadata documentation. Specifically, for a Proteomic dataset, associated metadata will be compliant with MIAPE standard (<http://www.psidev.info/node/91>). This

will ensure that our produced data can be analysed together with other data types during the project and following project completion.

Vaccine testing (**WP3**) will follow the guidelines of the European Pharmacopoeia for vaccines and ethical review approval for animal experimentation with power analysis. Challenge testing with live animals will follow methodologies that have already been used by the participating teams following the guidelines of 3R. Special care will be given to the reduction of the number of animals required for *in vivo* testing.

Omics data of **WP5** metadata will contain info about the sequencing platform used, sample treatment, source and location of isolation, and processing. Excel data regarding fish trials will be accompanied by information about the fish species, age, feeding regime, institute where experimentation took place, and equipment used.

Keywords will be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use. These will include task-specific keywords and when possible, keywords from the list of terms drawn from the U.S. National Library of Medicine's collection of Medical Subject Headings (MeSH). Metadata will be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed, adhering to appropriate metadata standards and using semantic terms to allow data consumers to find, aggregate, and analyse submitted data.

2.2 Making data accessible

To encourage re-use and further application of project results, data will be made accessible via **open access platforms** for verification and re-use, unless the data owner can justify why data cannot be made openly accessible. Where it is determined that a database should be kept confidential, the reasons for doing so will be included in an updated version of the DMP.

Data will be deposited in a trusted repository (Zenodo, <https://zenodo.org/communities/cure4aqua/>) and for long-term data preservation and sharing, -omics data will be submitted to ENA, GEO, *etc.*, public databases hosted by NCBI/ EBI/ SIB. The temporary storage of data obtained from fish cages and tanks monitoring will be stored in HCMR and BIOCEANOR servers, as well as in the platform of the AquaReal project (<https://cure4aqua.aquareal-bioceanor.com/login>).

Molecular data will be downloaded from public repositories hosted by NCBI (**WP6, WP7**), and then stored in Zenodo (currently Zenodo accepts up to 50 GB per dataset, but there is no size limit on communities). In addition, **WP7** will use the cloud storage box for all WP7 data: <https://uocbox.ict.uoc.gr/>.

At this stage of Cure4Aqua (M18), no additional arrangements with the identified repositories where the data will be deposited had to be made. Because the chosen repositories adhere to international data reporting standards, all deposited data will have an assigned identifier, resolved as a digital object.

All data will be made openly available, except for the limited period to ensure the novelty of publication, or longer in cases of concern related to commercial and patenting issues. At this project stage, there are some legal and contractual obligations for specific beneficiaries to keep their data

closed. Cure4Aqua data protection will be managed with the help of the Intellectual Property Use and Dissemination Committee (IUPDC), a consultative body that will advise the Consortium on the management of results, among the rest. *i.e.*, IUPDC will assist in identifying results, including data that could be the subject matter of protection, use or dissemination, based on publications and activity reports issued by activity leaders.

The **embargo for data** will be dictated by the time length necessary to publish the scientific publication and will vary from case to case, depending on the complexity of tasks/ methodology and scientific scope. In case the data will be protected by the patent, the scientific publication will not be published, including respective data, before the patent is granted. This will also vary from case to case, depending on the extensiveness of patent database searches and countries intended for the patent. Potential patentable data will include vaccines (**WP3**), alternative treatments (**WP5**) and diagnostics (**WP6**). From WP6, aptamers may be included in or converted into patentable biosensors, qPCR on chip cartridges and DNA extraction methods adapted to particular materials may also be a matter of IP protection. In **WP7**, the digital tool for on-site welfare assessment of GSB and ESB has patenting potential.

Otherwise, the data will be accessible through a free and **standardized access protocol** with a computer and the internet, *i.e.*, clicking on a specific link, as Cure4Aqua will use http(s) or ftp. This is a high-level interface to a low-level protocol called tcp, that the computer executes to load data in the user's web browser. In addition, this allows data retrieval without specialised or proprietary tools or communication methods. For highly sensitive data, it will not be possible to provide secure access through a fully mechanised protocol, therefore, Cure4Aqua will provide an email, the official telephone number of a contact person who can discuss access to the data, during and after the end of the project. This contact protocol will be clear and explicit in the metadata. The identity of the person accessing Cure4Aqua data will be ascertained by requesting the users to create a user account for a repository, which has been done already for Cure4Aqua partners using Zenodo. This will allow us to authenticate the owner (or contributor) of each dataset, and to potentially set user-specific rights. Data generated by FGCZ with restricted access will be managed by B-Fabric. For project-specific access, *i.e.*, only for members of an analytical project that have access to project data, the authentication account was already created. Within each project permissions will be granted based on individual users and their roles in the project.

At this project stage, Cure4Aqua does not have a **data access committee** (*e.g.*, to evaluate/ approve access requests to personal/ sensitive data), but relies on the protocol developed within the Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (PDEC) (M6, M54).

Metadata will be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement. It will contain information to enable the user to access the data. The data will remain available and findable in the public repository as long as the public repositories are viable, which also guarantees the long-term availability of metadata. In the case of B-Fabric, long-term storage of meta-information associated with all analytical projects will be possible. In case the software will be necessary to access or read the data from Cure4Aqua, documentation or references about the software will be included. The relevant software in open-source code will be available only if this does not contradict partners' IP rights. Omics data generated by SUSHI will be fully documented, reproducible and reusable, since the results are always accompanied by the executed analysis scripts,

the version numbers of the software used, as well as the input and the parameters. For custom analysis, analysis scripts will be stored together with the result files as metadata. Customized scripts will also be version-controlled using the FGCZs git server (<https://gitlab.bfabric.org>).

2.3 Making data interoperable

Cure4Aqua will follow community-endorsed **interoperability best practices** and use common standard formats for data and metadata. Standards (see under 2.1) will ensure that produced data can be analysed together with other data types.

As datasets are identified and collected, updates on standards for (meta)data creation will be outlined in the following DMP versions. In case other files will be obtained they will be converted to more commonly used ontologies.

To provide a “common understanding” of digital objects employing a language for knowledge representation to be used to represent these objects, Cure4Aqua will use a language with a formal specification, *i.e.*, those in which the syntax and grammar are defined in a precise way, and whose knowledge representation language specifications are shared and accessible, so others can read the specifications and learn the language. Ideally, the language will be useful in more than one scenario.

To describe data and metadata, the vocabularies that provide the terms or concepts that are adequate to represent their content will be used. These vocabularies will adhere to FAIR guidelines as well. The controlled vocabulary to describe datasets will be documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers, and this will be documented to be easily findable and accessible by anyone who uses the dataset.

Data will include qualified cross-references to other data, if the generated dataset builds on a previously generated dataset, or if the previous dataset is necessary to complete the new data, or if complementary information is stored in a different dataset (*e.g.*, other data from the Cure4Aqua project, or datasets from previous research), and metadata will follow DataCite’s metadata standard. All datasets will be properly cited by their globally unique and persistent identifiers, and included in the article’s reference list, allowing identification and access to any dataset in a publication.

2.4 Increase data re-use

For the most part, it is expected that there are no **limits** or licensing requirements to the data sharing or re-use by third parties, in particular after the end of the project. In other cases, we will endeavour to use the most open solution possible and a creative common (CC) license that is suitable for data sharing. Methods or software tools needed to access and use data include the standard Microsoft package, LibreOffice (freeware), R (freeware), BioEdit (freeware), Internet Browsers (freeware), GraphPad v8, Olympus’ free OlyVIA software, statistical packages: RevMan (freeware), comprehensive meta-analysis (licenced), SPSS (licenced), STATA (licenced), Silico (licenced), Anylogic (licenced), etc.

Data will be deemed useful for **reuse**, since the context under which the data was generated will be richly described in form of the supplementary data, such as experimental protocols, explanatory procedures, measured variables and additional details that might appear irrelevant. These supplementary data will accompany respective scientific publications. Omics datasets generated by FGCZ will be also accompanied by supplementary files attached to respective publications. These will

be openly available in appropriate digital data repositories that conform to the FAIR Data principles and are maintained by a non-profit organization. These specific datasets will be shared via domain-specific public repositories.

For **visibility and valorisation** of data, DOIs to appropriate records will be linked to the affiliations' publication repository, laboratories' webpage, researcher profile pages, as well as on researchers' ORCID IDs.

In the case of -omics data curated by FGCZ, data in the repositories will be stored following the funder's data policies. The retention schedule for data will be 10 years from the date of deposition in the first instance, with extensions applied to datasets, which are subsequently accessed.

Data will be accompanied by **details on data provenance**, such as data origin/ history, who to cite and/ or how to acknowledge the authors, and data workflow/ methodology. For -omics data, FGCZ via B-Fabric keeps track of all samples and meta-information regarding sample treatment and processing in the wet lab. Sequencing data analysed using the FGCZ SUSHI framework will be fully documented, reproducible and reusable, since the results are always accompanied by the executed analysis scripts, the version numbers of the software used, as well as the input and parameters. For custom analysis, analysis scripts will be version-controlled using the FGCZ's git server (<https://gitlab.bfabric.org>).

Data will be subjected to **quality assurance** processes. Data normalization protocols including measurement standards, data collection templates and formats, and safe digital storage will be used. Omics data at FGCZ will be generated respecting the applicable standard operating procedures (SOPs). Quality of analytical qPCR on chip data will be guaranteed through calibration and comparison with laboratory standard qPCR. This will be achieved by employing an appropriate experimental design, recording data meticulously, and validating data through the use of controls, replicates, and blinded approaches. All measurement instruments will be operated by expert personnel. Quality of analytical data will be guaranteed through the calibration of devices and comparison with internal standards. Appropriate experimental design, data recording and data validation (controls, randomization/ blinding, sampling/ replicates, experimental versus hypothesis driven-protocol) will ensure **internal validity**.

3. Other research outputs

Other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout Cure4Aqua, either digital (*e.g.*, software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (*e.g.*, new nanocarriers, aptamers, reagents, vaccines, media, cell lines, etc.) are foreseen in all scientific WPs. Their management will be addressed specifically in time of their delivery in line with the Grant Agreement and FAIR principles.

4. Allocation of resources

The DMP will include arrangements around responsibilities and costs for curation and preservation. Partners will mostly make use of free data repositories (*e.g.*, Zenodo, Centre for Information and Communication Technologies Infrastructure and Services) or use organisation subscriptions to domain-specific data repositories. Responsible teams for data management and quality assurance depend on each dataset. All data will be handled only by qualified researchers under strict

confidentiality agreements, assuring that data access, data protection and privacy standards will comply with national and European regulations. In all processing of personal data, we will comply with the principles set out in the EU GDPR. The estimated cost for making data or other research outputs FAIR in Cure4Aqua (e.g., direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, and open access) is 13,000 euros. Each partner will cover costs related to their data from their project funding, and partners' main contacts/ principal investigators in collaboration with respective WP leader are responsible for data management in Cure4Aqua Zenodo. The AquaReal platform will provide long term storage of meta-information.

Omics data curated at FGCZ will be secured for 10 years and will include the maintenance of digital security copies (300 €/ year). Public repositories will secure long-term data and metadata preservation.

5. Data Security

Standard provisions offered by the public repositories (for long term preservation) where data will be stored will be in place, including data recovery as well as secure storage/ archiving and transfer of sensitive data. The same will be in place for data stored at partners' affiliations. Lab books will be stored securely in the PI's office for a minimum of 20 years, in line with BBSRC guidelines, for example. Other information (data, images, project documentation, etc.) will be stored electronically on secure servers located in locked, air-conditioned server rooms at each partner institute (stored for at least 10 years) and on an offsite, long-term storage server. Data will be collected according to standard operating procedures in formats that are open, non-proprietary and in common use by the scientific community. Stored data will be backed up daily and will only be accessible by authorized personnel. For omics data stored at FGCZ, data access and security will be managed by B-Fabric. B-Fabric provides project-specific access to databases and data files. Additionally, within each analytical project, permission is granted based on the user and his role in the project. All data generated at or transferred to the FGCZ are physically stored by the University of Zurich and access is managed by FGCZ personnel.

6. Ethics

Data/ information relating to biological material and disease outbreak data obtained from fish farmers may be deemed as sensitive and could impact data sharing, especially if obtained under an MTA. Ethical dimensions of Cure4Aqua will involve human participants for empirical research for social and human science research (**WP2, WP7, WP8**), which will involve personal data collection and processing (e.g., sociodemographic such as age, gender, or nationality but also people's attitudes and perceptions) to evaluate the farm performance, operational costs, welfare indicators, scoring of QoL and willingness to pay. The data collected in these studies (online questionnaires) will adhere to ESOMAR standards to guarantee respondents complete anonymity of their data. The research will not involve the collection of sensitive personal data such as ethnicity, religion or political ideology. Cure4Aqua will involve the collection and processing of personal data. For this, participation in all activities will be voluntary and the purpose of the study and use of the data will be clearly explained to all participants, and a signed informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation will be obtained. A specific and detailed description of the planned activities, the purposes and methods of data processing and all the other content legally required by national law will be provided. The processing of personal data will be carried out only for the specific purposes of the Cure4Aqua activities, and data collected will not be disseminated in any way or disclosed to third parties that are

not formally involved in the research activities. For data processing, both with and without the use of electronic means, the most rigorous security measures will be adopted to ensure the integrity, confidentiality and control of the data submitted.

7. Other issues

Other national/ funder/ sectorial/ departmental procedures for data management will be specified at the time of the delivery of data that will be specifically related to these procedures, if any.

8. Conclusion

- Cure4Aqua DMP follows the rights and responsibilities related to data management as set in article 17 Grant Agreement
- All research data generated in the action is managed responsibly and in line with the FAIR principles
- The application of this document is the responsibility of all Cure4Aqua project partners
- Adhering to the maxim "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" when dealing with data, Cure4Aqua will develop DMP as a living document, which will be regularly updated

Appendix

N/A

Curing EU aquaculture
by co-creating health
and welfare innovations

Project Coordinator

Ivona Mladineo | ivona.mladineo@paru.cas.cz

Project Manager

Anna Holčáková | anna.holcakova@paru.cas.cz

Press and Communications

Karla Corrales | karla@erinn.eu

Website: cure4aqua-project.eu

X: [@Cure4Aqua_EU](https://twitter.com/Cure4Aqua_EU)

LinkedIn: [Cure4Aqua](https://www.linkedin.com/company/cure4aqua)

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